

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF LANGUAGE AND CULTURE HARMONY

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Annotation: *This article discusses the socio-philosophical and conceptual aspects of the language and culture of the thinker. Philosophical views on language culture are analyzed.*

Key words: *Language, culture, conceptual, communicative, speech, intellectual, verbal communication, integration, language development, internationalization, language development, social communicative.*

Introduction: A language is a specific form of manifestation of spiritual culture. Consequently, language serves to communicate, strengthen knowledge, exchange information, and make people understand each other. Speech, which is constructed using all the means of language and their possibilities effectively, is a cultural speech. Speech culture, on the other hand, applies to the communication of that language. The more negative this situation is, the more indifferent it is to its use, the lower the cultural level of speech. Conversely, the higher the attitude, the more cultural the speech.

The attitude of the speaker or writer to the possibilities of language, the states of thought, consciousness, being in the process of his communication, express the interdependence of language and culture. Speech culture contributes to the development of the philosophical content of language, the culture of conscious understanding of language, its rules, the culture of clearly expressive communication.

Literature review: Another task in ensuring the development of spiritual culture today is to maintain the purity of language. Indeed, "the cultural and historical experience of each nation, which preserves its uniqueness, national spirit, character, unity, is passed down from generation to generation through language." [1] In this sense, the preservation of the purity of the national language has an impact on the process of understanding the national identity, its consistency, as well as the development of spiritual culture.

Language is a means of uniting a nation, distinguishing it from other nations, and creating opportunities for learning through the

exchange of information. At present, at a time when our country is engaged in a broad dialogue with the peoples and nations of the world, the issue of maintaining the purity of our language is one of the most important, complex and urgent tasks. Indeed, its development has a positive impact on the formation of national pride, which in turn has a positive impact on the development of national spiritual culture.

Language culture has a conceptual character as a social phenomenon. The concept of "language culture" itself reflects, firstly, the dialectical nature of the relationship between the language system and communicative activity, and secondly, the individual features of social and speech activity in the language system. The above-mentioned principles of language culture can also be seen as components of the general characteristics of the individual. In studying the status of the language culture of the speaker, it is taken into account how he follows the socio-cultural rules. In determining these rules, the age, sex, education, social origin, social and economic status of the person are taken into account.

The language has changed and enriched over time. The interdependence of language and culture has allowed the development of people's diverse experiences to be passed down from generation to generation. As a result, science, culture, technology have developed, that is, human society has developed.

If we consider the interrelation of language and culture as a historical phenomenon, it requires the common cultural features of multilingualism and the linguistic aspects of the problem of universal language. In this regard, J. Steiner said: "Any linguistic act takes place over a period of time. No semantic form occurs outside the time frame. By using any word, we can say that we are awakening its previous history, forcing it to resonate historically as before. Any text comes into being at a particular historical time. Reading the whole text means restoring the content expressed in it, the goals and objectives that determine the authenticity of the speech. "[2]

In our view, if the language is viewed only in an abstract synchronous state, and only the internal structural relations of lexical units are taken into account, the original content of speech structures can never be understood. Language and time are interrelated. This provides an opportunity to address the sources of factors that shape the worldviews of people living in different parts of the world.

J. Steiner also studied the traditional culture of the peoples of Europe and put forward a unique idea that scientifically interprets the characteristics of these cultures. In his view, European culture and civilization can be interpreted as a heritage "transcribed" from samples of ancient Mediterranean culture. And all the innovations that emerge in this environment are based on the same classical templates. His views on the impact on cultural development, such as "Perhaps cultural traditions are more firmly entrenched in our syntax and our lives, whether we like it or not, remain a translation of our personal and social past" [3] are noteworthy.

The language belongs to every national culture, preserves it as a stable reality of folk culture in socio-cultural processes, protects it from external assimilation and internal decline. There are as many nations, peoples, peoples, tribes as there are languages on earth. People and language are twin concepts, inseparable, and if they are separated, both lose their identity. Even if a nation joins another nation, its language becomes a dead language.

The emergence of language is associated with "internal" and "external" needs. While the external need is related to the birth of the will to communicate in people, the internal need is to create the conditions for the spiritual and intellectual development of the nation. Indeed, at the present stage of language development, there are various processes such as standardization, modelling, stratification, "intellectualization", globalization, internationalization and democratization, which do not affect the general language system, its speech activity.

The language embraces subjectivity and objectivity in itself. On the one hand, the man accepts language as an inheritance, and on the other hand, he constantly "reshapes" language. In the speech, language is recreated each time. Linguistic traditions, on the other hand, ensure the creative ability of each generation and individual. Both the individual and generation influence the process of linguistic creativity. After all, they introduce innovations into the language, and these innovations are radically different from previous traditions. As a result, there is a two-way relationship of necessity and freedom in language, which, firstly, limits the influence of linguistic traditions and, secondly, provides the influence of the society in which the language is spoken.

Standardization or standardization is an attempt to standardize spoken and written language styles, to bridge the gap between them. This implies the gradual disappearance of regional dialects as a result of the influence of literary language on dialects and interactions. The beginning of this kind of process leads to the "impoverishment" of the language of fiction, the inability of its grammar and vocabulary to serve as a model and norm, people are more exposed to the language of the press, radio, television, advertising than fiction. The result is the problem of harmonizing the norms of literary language with the language of the media. The main reason for such global phenomena is the integration in the process of labour activity.

This tradition in the development of language is the result of scientific and technological progress, the emergence of new professions, modern means of communication. For example, the phenomenon of lexical stratification associated with the creation of new terms in the vocabulary of all languages of the world, the proliferation of synonymous, homonymous words, the growing role of contextual meaning is becoming more widespread.

The "intellectualization" of language is a large-scale penetration of the features of a common language of communication, a scientific language. In this case, the desire of linguistic communication to clarity, unambiguousness, to save means of expression is observed. One of the reasons for this is the development of science and technology, the deepening changes taking place in society.

Intellectualization is reflected in the lexical, phonological and morphological layers of the language system. For example, in modern German this phenomenon can be seen in the following processes: 1) a large number of specific scientific and technical terms in the dictionary (for example, "Plast" - originally the term belonged to organic chemistry, now it means "artificial fabric".); 2) the lexical units present in the language have a special semantic meaning.

The internationalization of a language is the enrichment of a common language with new words that exist in several languages and are used in the same form and meaning. English plays an important role in the internationalization of languages. New international words are also emerging on the basis of Latin, Greek and other languages. For example, in German: "Autopilot" - autopilot, "Antikriegs film" - anti-war film; Uzbek: "monitoring", "lyceum", "traffic", "gender".

The democratization of language is the convergence of written and spoken language. This phenomenon is reflected in the entry of compounds in spoken language into written speech. Based on the above, the study of the issue of "language culture", which represents the relationship between language and culture, is noted as an urgent problem. Also, as we study the relationship between language and culture in the context of globalization, we must not forget that culture is a multifaceted and multifaceted phenomenon. In turn, language, as a complex device, does not enter into the same relationship with different parts of culture. However, the influence of language on different elements of culture is not decisive.

Man's language culture plays an important role in his spiritual world. It reflects the peculiarities of the historical stage, the system, this or that socio-economic device. They are reflected in the construction of language in changes in its basic linguistic features, in the perception of stylistic means, in specific forms of communication, as well as in the functions of language in socio-cultural activities. Therefore, the concept of "language culture" has had different meanings in different historical periods.

Language culture is, first of all, the norms of language, its vocabulary, phraseological resources, which are established on the basis of scientific conclusions and the results of social practice, ensuring the accuracy of linguistic thinking. To study the phenomenon of language culture in terms of its development, it is necessary to refer to the following areas of research:

First, spelling, research on the reform of spelling on a scientific basis in order to cleanse the modern system of archaic features;

Second, research into the sound, tone side of speech. These studies cover not only orthoepy but also the role of pronunciation in the implementation of communication.

Third, the problem of language culture also applies to grammar. However, in a grammatical system, language culture takes a different direction. Indeed, the theory of language culture is incapable of independently creating a morphological norm. The norm arises in the language system itself. The influence of language culture on it is indirect;

Fourth, the study of this area within the context of language culture requires special attention to the differences between oral and written speech syntax;

Fifth, the study of language culture in terms of stylistic differences;

Sixth, the study of language culture from a semantic point of view is concerned with the standardization of vocabulary content and the identification of opportunities for the development of a system of terms.

All-natural languages are universal systems of expression. With the help of language, any community standing at different stages of cultural development can meet all types of communicative needs. One of the characteristic features of modern literary languages, for example, is the "internationalization" and "intellectualization" mentioned above. As a result, in all countries, there is a growing focus not only on national self-awareness and the mother tongue, its culture but also on the enrichment of the vocabulary of languages through other languages.

If we look at interlingual relations from the point of view of the theory of linguistic culture, we can cite the following exemplary opinion of academician L.V. Shcherba: If you have the opportunity to express a new concept with your own tools (word formation or compound words), of course, it is better not to fill your vocabulary with foreign elements. However, the boundaries of these two cases are so thin that it can be seen with a special linguistic, literary intuition. However, this intuition is not necessarily mystical, and it is formed as a result of philological education".[4]

Language culture has a common feature as a sociolinguistic phenomenon. Linguistic culture is a conscious and solid mastery of the basic laws and peculiarities of literary language, its social norms (orthoepic, orthographic, lexical, morphological, syntactic means). This can also include functional styles of literary language. The scope of the interaction of language and culture also includes events related to the place of language in society. At the same time, the literary language, which deals with all dialects, is civilized.

Research methodology: The concept of "language culture" should be studied concerning the culture of the speakers. Because the concept of "language culture" reflects the dialectical relationship of language system and speech activity on the one hand, and social and individual activity through language and speech, on the other hand.

Analysis and results. These aspects of language culture constitute a set of individual personality traits. Therefore, the formation of

language culture plays an important role in the process of education and upbringing of the individual. Also, the development of socio-communicative activities on the basis of certain rules, the solution of theoretical and practical issues related to language culture and language policy are one of the important areas of cultural policy.

The conceptual development of language and culture depends on both social and external factors. Social factors include a certain level of development of society, traditions of integration in the economy, internationally, in science and culture. These factors combine with external factors to form a single whole. That is, a complete theory of language culture is created through a scientific understanding of the national language, primarily literary language.

Conclusion: The richness of world culture lies in its diversity. The mirror of culture, its foundation is language. It is hard to imagine the formation and spread of a languageless culture around the world. Language has its own laws, and these laws are different from the laws of thinking. Language is a means of stability and change in society. It serves to strengthen stability and ensure resilience. The unity and essence of language and culture are that languages develop the knowledge of people in society.

Because the general culture of a person is inextricably linked with language. One of the most important achievements in the development of human culture is its language. The mutual conceptual development of language and culture is of great importance in the changes in social life, the influence of national consciousness, socio-cultural factors.

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